

Causes, Adverse Effects, and Preventative Measures of Water Pollution

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Abstract:

One major problem that humanity has been confronting recently is water quality. Since water cannot be substituted for other environmental elements, it is kept apart from them. The fundamental dynamics of the life and economic cycles are made up of the water cycle. Water resources are finite and subject to numerous adverse consequences caused by humans. Water contamination is one of the important research topics that has drawn the interest of environmentalists and researchers because to its profound impact on the lives of people, animals, and plants. It is more closely related to soil and air contamination than it is less dangerous. This study focuses mostly on the sources of various water pollutants and their present condition in the environment and ecosystem. It discusses the scientific developments made recently to address water pollution. It is anticipated that this study will add to the body of knowledge on the topic and lower the degree of contamination in water resources.

Keywords: Water pollution; Environment; Phosphorus concentrations; Animal; Sources

1. Introduction:

One of the renewable resources needed to support all life forms, food production, economic growth, and overall wellbeing is water. It is a genuinely unique gift from nature to humanity, impossible to substitute for the majority of its purposes, expensive to transport, and difficult to decontaminate. Because it may be used for diversion, transportation, storage, and recycling, water is also one of the most manageable natural resources. Water is very useful to humans because of all these qualities [1, 2]. In the eyes of the majority of researchers and interested parties, water pollution research is crucial. The fundamental alterations it brings about in the lives of people, animals, plants, soil, and the environment at large are what give it its significance. The study focused on the problem of water pollution caused by the disposal of solid, organic, and liquid wastes into lakes and streams that are home to hazardous substances including lead, mercury, and metals. One of the most significant forms of pollution caused by nuclear activity is radioactive pollution, which arises when elements escape into the water and transform into a poisonous chemical. Because many companies do not use fertilizers and pesticides in accordance with industrial drainage standards, the waste ends up in the water. Water contamination is also significantly impacted by garbage leaks from residential buildings.

As the primary sources of water pollution, it also addresses sanitation sources, highlighting the key factors that contribute to groundwater pollution as well as the steps involved in treating and purifying it.

Pollution is defined as any adverse change to an environmental component brought about entirely or in part by industrial and vital human activity, as compared to the pre-intervention state of nature. These changes start with variations in radiation levels, energy levels, and unwelcome biological, physical, and chemical changes that occur in the biosphere, which is our immediate environment and the environment in which all other living things reside. These changes can have an impact on the ecological balance through the production of food, water, air, and various agricultural products [3]. Water is one of the most vital natural resources for any economic structure because it is essential to life and social development. Without water, it is impossible to imagine life as we know it on Earth, as water is the true synonym for life and is necessary for all living things, including humans. Water is also necessary for agriculture, food production, drink production, and energy production. It is sufficient to say that water makes up at least 75% of the human body and roughly 90% of plant composition [4]. Water is essential for linking different parts of the world through various forms of maritime transportation, and it is the only source of fish richness, one of the world's most important food sources. The significance of water does not end here [4, 5].

The need for freshwater has increased dramatically over the past few decades as a result of both the accelerated rate of industrialization and the rapid growth of the population [6]. Most agricultural development operations pose a risk to human health, especially when it comes to overuse of fertilizers and unhygienic circumstances [7]. Furthermore, the improvement of water quality and the reduction of water pollution have been progressively hampered by inadequate water supplies. Researchers from the government and scientific community have focused on water contamination. Because of the severe water pollution and limited water resources worldwide, it is imperative to safeguard the purity of river water [8]. The main way to stop these bad impacts is to educate people about the environment and the harm that comes from water contamination. These kinds of investigations can also highlight the subject's sensitivity and significance.

2. Reasons why water is contaminated: It is also known as the quantitative and qualitative change that happens to one or more elements of the environment, which would harm the life of the organism and weaken the ecosystems ability to continue its production. Excessive amount of human waste production and road construction also responsible for air pollution as well as water pollution [9, 10]. Numerous types of contamination harm water supplies. Water supplies will soon run out if pollution levels rise more. 88 emerging nations account for 40% of the global population. The lack of water is a major obstacle because of its social and economic advancement. With so many people on the planet and so many varied things they do, freshwater use for a variety of uses has steadily climbed.

Water pollution arises from the disposal of sediments and organic waste that deplete oxygen, primarily from untreated urban sewers and industrial drains. These areas are also the source of

trace contaminants, which are hazardous compounds and metals like mercury, zinc, lead, and cadmium. Thermal pollution is one kind of water pollution that arises from discharging waste water from factories, power plants, and cooling towers into water streams. This leads to an imbalance in the water environment and elevated temperatures [11]. Phosphorus concentrations in urban basins typically rise with urbanization. Nutrient loadings into urban streams are caused by increasing imperviousness, increased runoff from urbanized surfaces, and higher discharges from cities and industries. As a result, the primary cause of stream damage is no longer agriculture but rather urbanization [12].

Agrochemicals, pesticides, petrochemicals, hydrocarbons, heavy metals, radioactive elements, and other contaminants can be created during their use in household, agricultural, or industrial settings through the concentration and modification of naturally existing substances. Many of the compounds are completely man-made and do not exist in nature. For instance, there are significant issues with water quality and the environment as a result of the synthesis of different pesticides, surfactants, plastics, and petrochemicals [13]. Farmers also employ chemical fertilizers, which enrich the soil with nutrients that run off into rivers and seas and enhance the fertilization effect of sewage. When combined, fertilizers and sewage can greatly accelerate the growth of algae or plankton in vast regions of rivers, lakes, or seas, a phenomenon known as an algal bloom that lowers the water's dissolved oxygen concentration and kills other organisms like fish [14].

Low sanitation facility among village and city people in developing countries with unwarranted use of water are one of the big causes of water pollution [15]. The enormous amounts of organic and non-biodegradable trash that are produced every day make solid waste management an ineffective endeavor. Consequently, most of India's rubbish is disposed of in an improper manner, which raises the pollution load in surface and groundwater channels. Because it releases essential elements into the environment, like phosphorus and nitrogen, which are necessary for plant and animal growth, sewage can be used as fertilizer.

Temperature variations have a negative impact on aquatic biota and water quality. Human activity is the primary cause of the majority of thermal pollution in water. The release of large amounts of heat into water bodies by various industries, including nuclear power and electric power plants, steel melting factories, coal fire power plants, and boilers, can result in significant thermal pollution and alter the physical, chemical, and biological properties of the receiving water bodies. Elevated temperatures lead to a decrease in the oxygen concentration in water, disrupting many physiological processes such as respiration, digestion, and reproductive cycles, ultimately creating challenges for aquatic organisms.

Sea water is heavily contaminated when oil spills into the ocean from cargo tankers transporting gasoline, diesel, and its derivatives. Water that contains iron and magnesium takes on a rust-like hue. In surface water, it is pervasive. Unless it is present in significant amounts, it does not harm anything. Water is filtered to remove dangerous microorganisms using fluorine and chlorine. Nevertheless, they interact with hydrocarbons when they include chlorocarbons that cause cancer [16].

Nuclear activities and the attempt to dispose of nuclear waste enhance the risk of this kind of contamination. It is possible for radioactive elements to escape into bodies of water, where they are then absorbed by living things and passed on to people, having a variety of genetic impacts [17]. The presence of radioactive elements in water results in radioactive contamination. They are divided into two categories: little dosages that momentarily speed up metabolism and huge amounts that progressively harm the body and result in genetic mutation. The usage of radioisotopes in medicine and research, radioactive sediment, radioactive minerals extracted from the earth, radioactive power plants, and waters used in nuclear atomic facilities are all potential sources.

Figure 1: Different ways of water pollution, Source: weebly.com

Figure 2. Industrial area pollution into water, Copyright from Breaban et al., [24]

Figure 3. Causes of river pollution

3. Negative impacts on animal: The entire ecosystem is negatively impacted by water pollution, but people and marine life are particularly hard hit. Increased water pollution has a negative impact on plant development, making it impossible for plants to absorb the minerals required for photosynthesis and preventing forests from expanding. When wastes are mixed with sewage water that is already polluted, significant contamination results. Infections by bacteria, viruses, and parasites are also brought on by dirty water. Algal growth damages the ecology by preventing fish and other marine life from absorbing oxygen. In particular, the unrestricted flow of hazardous liquids in the environment contaminates groundwater and soil. The lives of the local fauna are at risk due to soil degradation. The lives of marine life are negatively impacted by the release of sewage water into the ocean. The primary indicators of pollution, inappropriate habitation, overfishing, and inappropriate technology usage are the declining numbers and species of marine and freshwater life.

Water contamination and health issues are closely related. Human to human transmission of several waterborne diseases and illnesses is occurring. Numerous illnesses, including cancer, reproductive system disorders, diarrheal disease, neurological disorders, cardiovascular disease, and respiratory disorders are among the health risks linked to contaminated water [18-20]. Water pollution also has serious effects on human health. Environmental risk factors that cause diseases with high mortality in developing countries include unsafe water, lack of

wastewater system and inadequate hygiene practices. Intestinal diseases are among the evidentiary results of these factors. Diseases such as hepatitis, diarrhea and cholera stand out as the main diseases caused by water pollution.

In acidified water, the population of disintegrating microorganisms such as bacteria and fungus decreases, hence slowing down the pace at which organic matter decomposes and impacting the cycling of nutrients. For the majority of aquatic organisms, pH 7.0 is crucial. Below this pH, species diversity decreases while the quantity and diversity of acid-tolerant organisms rise. When water first begins to acidify, filamentous algae multiply quickly and create a thick mat. Since acidic water typically affects macrophytes' roots, which leads to poor plant development, macrophytes are typically absent from such environments. Water that has been acidified contains *Potamogeton pectinalis*. In acidic water, plants with short root systems are shown to be badly harmed, but plants with deep roots and rhizomes appear to be less impacted.

Plants can absorb chemical contaminants through their roots when they accumulate in terrestrial or aquatic settings. Phytotoxicity is the poisoning of plants by harmful substances. Plants experiencing phytotoxicity may exhibit stunted development, withering seedlings, and dead patches on their leaves. For instance, because mercury compounds accumulate in plant bodies and roots and cause bio-accumulation, mercury poisoning—which is commonly linked to fish—can also impact aquatic plants. Mercury levels rise across the food chain as a result of animals consuming contaminated food [21].

4. Ways to Prevent Water Pollution [22]:

- ❖ Install a toilet dam or plastic bottle in your toilet tank.
- ❖ Install a water-efficient showerhead (2.5 gallons or less per minute).
- ❖ Take short showers and draw less water for baths.
- ❖ Fill the washing machine to the brim with clothing. Instead of using hot water for washing, use warm water for rinsing. When possible, wash with cold water. Dry the laundry by hanging it outside, if you can.
- ❖ To make the turf more drought-tolerant, cut it at least three inches high; for the healthiest grass, keep your mower sharp.
- ❖ Wash the vehicle less frequently or take it to a car wash where the water is cleaned and recycled, don't use the hose; instead, use a bucket of soapy water. Keep the hose fitted with a spring-loaded nozzle.
- ❖ Use less amount of plastics
- ❖ Reduce the usage of herbicides and insecticides.
- ❖ Have a rain garden or dry well installed.
- ❖ Rainwater collection ought to be done in order to keep the water table from dropping.
- ❖ To stop water contamination, the fundamental step is to raise public awareness of the issue. Therefore, awareness and education campaigns should include information on the value of water and pollution control strategies.

5. Necessity of clean water: Apart from oxygen, water is the one resource on which humans depend the most. Nevertheless, one in two people worldwide lack access to enough water for

proper sanitation, and one in three people lack access to clean drinking water. These communities frequently deal with two different types of issues. The first is the general scarcity of water. Access is the second issue. These rural villages frequently get their water from boreholes drilled by the government. Families may not be able to pay the usage charge, however this resource is occasionally available to the general public. Another problem is location. Women and children are usually the ones who have to gather water, and they often have to travel long distances to get safe water. They are prevented from engaging in long-term beneficial economic or educational endeavors since this consumes both their time and energy [23].

Water is rightly referred to be the "elixir of life." It is a necessary part of every known kind of life on Earth. The life of humans and many other species is in jeopardy if they do not have access to clean, safe drinking water. Nevertheless, not everyone has access to clean water, even though water is essential to our existence. This article explores the value of clean water and the reasons that water treatment is essential to maintaining human and environmental health and wellbeing. Water is essential for the removal of waste products and poisons from our bodies through perspiration and urine. This keeps our internal systems hygienic and operating at peak efficiency. Our bodies need water as a conduit to transfer vital nutrients throughout them. It eliminates waste and aids in the delivery of nutrients and oxygen to cells. Hydration in moderation promotes glowing, healthy skin. Skin that is dehydrated is more prone to wrinkles and can feel dry and uncomfortable. Water makes up around 60% of our body, and it is essential to every cell, tissue, and organ for effective operation. For several body processes, such as digestion, circulation, temperature control, and more, it is important to maintain adequate hydration.

6. Conclusion: Water is an essential resource for all living things since it is life itself and is necessary for all living things. Although it keeps them alive, contaminated water is extremely dangerous. Human health suffers greatly when they consume contaminated water. The main objective of environmental and water pollution education is to equip learners with knowledge, values and skills that promote the protection and conservation of the environment. To reduce pollution, seminars, workshops, and educational and awareness campaigns should be held. It is necessary to take action before a serious issue like this arises. Numerous detrimental repercussions of water pollution include illnesses, the demise of aquatic life, the financial burden of cleaning procedures, ecological collapse, and disruption of food chains.

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